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Autism spectrum disorders in children: risk factors

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the problem of autism in children and is currently becoming particularly relevant, since the number of such children is increasing every year. This article describes the risk factors of autism.

KEY WORDS: autism, characteristic signs, genetic and environmental factors, harmful factors during pregnancy and childbirth.

Introduction. Autism is a severe mental disorder, an extreme form of self-isolation. It is expressed in the withdrawal from contact with reality, the poverty of the expression of emotions. An autistic person is characterized by an inadequate response and a lack of social interaction.

Characteristic signs of autism:

1. A child with autism does not develop speech well, both receptive (understanding) and expressive. Often speech takes the form of echolalia (repetitions of elements of speech heard from others or on TV). Only simple unambiguous instructions are available for understanding ("sit down", "eat", "close the door", etc.). Abstract thinking lags behind in development, which manifests itself in misunderstanding of such elements of speech as pronouns (yours, mine, his, etc.), etc. The inability of the child to speak or understand speech is the most frequent complaint of parents during the initial examination of the child. Speech

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problems become apparent in the second year of a child's life.

2. The child behaves as if he had a clear deficit of sensations and perception – i.e. as if he is blind and deaf, but a more thorough examination reveals the safety of all sensory modalities. Parents of children with autism complain that it is very difficult for them to attract the attention of their kids. They usually do not maintain eye contact with their parents and/or do not turn their heads in response to the speech addressed to them.

3. Children with autism usually do not develop close emotional relationships with their parents. This is revealed in the first months of life, when parents discover that the child does not cling to the mother while in her arms, and sometimes resists physical contact, straining his back and trying to slip out of the parental embrace.

4. Children with autism do not play with toys, as ordinary children do. They do not show much interest in toys and do not engage in them in their free time. If they play, they often do it in a very peculiar way, for example, they turn the wheels of an overturned toy truck, twist a piece of rope, sniff or suck a doll. Inability to play with toys can be detected in the second year of life.

5. There are no or noticeably limited games with peers. The child may either not show interest in such games, or he may lack the necessary gaming skills and, as a rule, does not pay attention to other children, unless he participates in a simple "give-take" type of game. This sign is also easily detected in the second year of life.

6. Self-service skills in children with autism are absent or their development is extremely delayed. It is difficult for them to learn how to dress themselves, use the toilet and eat without help. These children do not recognize the usual danger well,

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and they need constant supervision so that they do not get seriously injured crossing a street with heavy traffic, playing with electrical equipment, etc.

7. Children with autism have very frequent outbursts of rage and aggression. This aggression can be directed at themselves when children bite their hands, bang their heads on the floor, furniture, or punch themselves in the face. Sometimes aggression is directed at others, and then children bite, scratch or beat their parents.

8. Children with autism can often demonstrate "self-stimulating" behavior in the form of ritual, repetitive stereotypical actions. They swing their whole body standing or sitting, clap their hands, rotate objects, stare at lights, fans and other rotating objects, line up objects in neat rows, jump and squat or spin in one place for a long time[8].

Autism was once considered a relatively rare disease. Recent epidemiological data have significantly changed this opinion. Based on a major study conducted by the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the prevalence of the disorder in the US was estimated as 1 case per 88 children (www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/data.html).

RAS is considered as a result of the interaction of genetic and environmental factors [3-6]. In particular, factors that increase the risk of pervasive development during conception include:

- the presence of cases of ASD, speech development disorders, severe mental disorders (schizophrenia, bipolar disorder in family history);
- * late (more than 30 years) age of the mother and/or father at the time of conception;
- conception of a child by in vitro fertilization. The late age of the father has a

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greater impact on the risk of ASD than the late age of the mother. Proper evidence has not been obtained that it is the late age of the mother, and not the associated disorders of pregnancy and the pathology of childbirth that increase the risk of pervasive development. Taking antidepressants by women during the year before conception is accompanied by a twofold, valproic acid salts — a fourfold increase in the risk of ASD. In vitro fertilization increases the risk of ASD in every way. There is no direct evidence that in vitro fertilization, and not the late age of the mother, is the cause of a higher incidence of diseases in ASD.

The effect of a number of harmful factors during pregnancy and childbirth is also associated with impaired neurodevelopment. All known teratogens cause congenital malformations, affecting embryogenesis during the first eight weeks after fertilization. Later harms have a greater impact on the severity of pervasive disorders than the likelihood of their occurrence. It has been proven that an increased risk of ASD in the presence of one or more adverse factors in the obstetric history: low birth weight (< 2500 g), low Apgar score at the 5th minute (< 6, < 7), gestational age at birth < 37 weeks, obstetric operations in the obstetric history. Various developmental abnormalities during pregnancy increase the likelihood of diagnosis of pervasive developmental disorder to the same extent, the risks of various factors are not summed up.

Smoking during pregnancy increases the risk of ASD by 2.6 times. The reliability of the diagnosis of ASD correlates with the hospitalization of the mother in the first trimester of pregnancy due to a viral infection, in the second trimester - a bacterial infection. Taking antibacterial and antiviral medications during pregnancy increases the risk of autism fourfold. There was a twofold increase in the risk of

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ASD disease in the children of mothers who used selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) during the year before delivery and a three-fold increase in the risk in the case of taking SSRIs in the first trimester of pregnancy. Mercury, cadmium, nickel, trichloroethylene, and vinyl chloride are the five environmental factors whose increased exposure is also associated with RAS.

Three more environmental risk factors—living in regions that are urbanized, located at higher latitudes or have high precipitation levels throughout the year, may be associated with insufficient insolation and the development of vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D plays an important role in repairing DNA damage and protecting the genome from oxidative stress, which is the main cause of it damage. Factors associated with vitamin D deficiency probably contribute to an increase in the frequency of new mutations and complicate the regeneration of genes.

The role of genetic factors in the genesis of autism is decisive and, according to experts, reaches 90% [1]. Genetic factors are heterogeneous, complex, and for the most part poorly understood. Evidence of the importance of the genetic factor in the genesis of ASD has been obtained from many sources, in particular from the results of twin studies. cited, cited by R. Mulet et al. in the article "Genetics of Autism" published in the journal Pediatrics, siblings whose probands suffer from autism have a disorder 50-200 times more common than in the general population. The exact mechanisms of action of genetic factors are studied using genomic screening, cytogenetic studies and evaluation of candidate genes [2]. Over the past two decades, numerous variants of gene polymorphism have been described, to varying degrees associated with ASD at individual loci 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 10, 15, 17 and the 22nd chromosome. Violations were detected in the locus 15kv11-13kv13. The

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gene polymorphism of loci 5p14.1 and 5p15 was found to have a negligible effect on the risk of autism manifestation. However, due to the described mutations, it is possible to explain no more than 10% of cases of ASD.

Conclusion: Thus, there are many factors contributing to the development of autism, within which genetic, prenatal factors, parent-dependent factors are considered significant.

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